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Integrating FAIR and open research data management practices in academic rewarding systems

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Executive summary

This work examines how open science practices and the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship can be more effectively integrated into the systems that recognise and reward academic work. It outlines the current academic reward system, recent proposals for responsible research assessment such as DORA, the Leiden Manifesto, and CoARA, and the specific challenges around recognising research data quality and research data metrics. The paper highlights how NFDI4Earth members – as researchers, members of academic societies, journal editors, and grant reviewers – can support the cultural shift required to reward FAIR and open research data practices alongside traditional publication metrics.

Contributions

Based on CRediT Contributor Roles, see <https://credit.niso.org/>.

AH: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

DN: Writing - review & editing

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1 Introduction

The Earth System Sciences (ESS) confront some of the most urgent and complex challenges of our time: climate change, biodiversity loss, water security, and extreme weather events. Addressing these issues requires robust, transparent, and reusable scientific evidence based on research data that can be integrated across disciplines, models, and scales. In this context, the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Wilkinson et al. 2016) and the broader objectives of Open Science (UNESCO 2021) are not optional ideals but practical necessities for accelerating discovery, enabling reproducibility, and maximising societal impact. Yet, despite growing infrastructure and an increasing number of policies supporting FAIR and open research data, widespread adoption remains uneven. A central barrier is the misalignment between researchers' FAIR and open data practices and the reward systems that drive researchers' decisions, many of which are relevant for building a professional career.

Reward systems encompass the formal and informal incentives that shape professional behaviour: hiring and promotion criteria, grant evaluation, publication metrics, institutional recognition, author guidelines, and community norms. Historically, these systems have privileged book and journal publications and novelty over openness and data curation (i.e., the process of managing research data throughout its lifecycle, involving organising, rigorously documenting, sharing, and preserving data) or software development. Without recalibrated incentives, data sharing and high-quality stewardship remain peripheral activities, often unfunded and undervalued.

Relevance for the Earth System Sciences

The urgency of reform is compounded in ESS by its truly international and interdisciplinary nature and the field's reliance on heterogeneous data sources (e.g., satellite observations, in situ measurements, lab experiments, remote sensing products, model outputs, and socio-environmental datasets) and diverse methods (quantitative, qualitative, mixed, ...) that must interoperate across formats, standards, institutional boundaries, and countries. A successful transformation of culture and practices within ESS would be close to achieving a systemic change. FAIR-aligned and open research practices reduce friction in data reuse and collaboration, foster interdisciplinary synthesis, and increase the return on investment in observational networks and modelling infrastructure. Moreover, transparent data management underpins trustworthy science, which is essential for informing public policy and maintaining societal trust in ESS findings (Milton and Possolo 2020; Guillen-Aguinaga et al. 2025).

2 NFDI4Earth as facilitator

To include FAIR and open research practices in research assessment schemes is part of most new proposals for reassessing the system of rewarding scholars¹. NFDI4Earth does align with these initiatives, as expressed in the NFDI4Earth Fairness and Openness Commitment (NFDI4Earth Consortium 2024). And although NFDI4Earth cannot directly change reward systems at research institutions or create incentives at funding agencies and publishers, it can raise awareness and help drive the cultural shift needed. The infrastructure and services built by NFDI4Earth can facilitate or highlight desirable practices, but the most promising support route in this respect is the activity of members involved in NFDI4Earth that hold positions of influence in various roles.

By leveraging people in these roles, NFDI4Earth can help indirectly to advance fairer recognition of research data and its management in research assessment. These roles are listed below, along with an outline of activities that can help to strengthen the role of FAIR and open data practices in research assessment schemes. Everyone who has a role to play here, should be encouraged to think about the issue and take action.

Take action: researchers in their institution

Researchers that serve in professorial appointment committees could advocate for FAIR and open research data practices to be taken into account when filling professorial posts (researchers and also research supporting staff). FAIR and open research data practices could be included in the list of criteria, applicants could be reminded to comment on this topic in application documents, job interviews, or hearings (for professorships). Independently, committee members can bring up these aspects in discussions, for example via the pervasive requirements for good scientific practice (gute wissenschaftliche Praxis, GWP), and contribute to weighing good practices higher than typical, traditional indicators.

When researchers are involved in academic self-governance, for example as vice-presidents or deans, they can advocate for FAIR and open research data practices to be incorporated into their institution's policies and institutional regulations on research evaluation. For members of

¹ DORA: "For the purposes of research assessment, consider the value and impact of all research outputs (including datasets and software) in addition to research publications..." <https://sfedora.org/read/>; CoARA: "...enabling recognition of all contributions to quality research by research units and institutions. Such recognition includes that of early sharing of data and results,..." <https://www.coara.org/agreement/the-commitments/>; Hong Kong Principles: "It also appears that promotion and tenure committees (PTCs) generally do not give sufficient importance to registering protocols and data analysis plans, full publishing of completed studies, or making data, code, and materials available [27]. These activities deserve to be credited in the assessment of researchers because they are essential for replicability, to make it possible to verify what was done, and to enable the reuse of data." (Moher et al. 2020).

research performing organisations outside of universities, this also applies to participation in cross-institutional working groups and broader organisational policies.

Many institutions in Germany have joined the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)² and/or signed DORA (San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment)³. If researchers work at such an institution, they can get involved in the local CoARA team (or DORA team, if existing). If the institution is not yet a member of CoARA / signer of DORA, researchers may encourage the relevant bodies in their institution to get involved.

Take action: members of Earth System Sciences academic societies

Members of Earth System Sciences academic societies, especially those in leadership roles, may want to set the topic on the agenda of their society. They may propose that the academic society signs a declaration like DORA or the NFDI4Earth Commitment, or joins CoARA. The discourse around such signatures/membership could initiate a working group on FAIR and open data practices and their possible integration into research assessment for their community, considering the specifics of their field and leveraging the network of institutions and groups that forms the society. The topic could also be taken up by DVGeo⁴, the umbrella organisation of Geosciences in Germany. Academic societies often publish scholarly journals and can reward or even require better practices in their guidelines and reviews (see below).

Take action: journal editors and article reviewers

Publications, particularly in academic journals, play a major role in research evaluation. Editors of academic journals can advocate to the journal's owners for the journal to have a robust and up-to-date data policy and for mechanisms to be put in place to ensure compliance with that policy. That is important because especially journals published by large commercial publishers often rely on broad generic policies without proper adaptation or resources for enforcement, such as expert reviewers or editors for data and methods. Reviewers of journal articles can familiarise themselves with the provisions of the respective journal's data policy and pay particular attention to this aspect when reviewing an article. Apart from that, reviewers can positively recognise FAIR and open data practices when reviewing research articles.

² <https://www.coara.org/national-chapters/coara-national-chapter-germany/>

³ <https://sfdora.org/signers/>

⁴ <https://www.dvgeo.org/english-abstract>

Take action: reviewers of grant applications

In addition to publication output, the number of and amount of awarded funding from research grants play an important role in evaluating researchers' work. Grant reviewers can ensure, as part of their role, that the funders' requirements regarding research data are fully met. If the funders have not yet established any provisions about research data, or if their policies are inadequate, reviewers may send recommendations to the funders and propose up-to-date policies, especially when they are not only reviewers but members of formal bodies within funding organisations, such as a DFG review board (Fachkollegium). In the challenging landscape of project-based funding where often more highly-ranked proposals are submitted than can be sponsored, aspects on FAIRness and openness may tip the scales regardless of their formal inclusion in criteria.

3 The current academic reward system

The contemporary system for rewarding scholars is a mix of formal criteria and informal norms that together shape careers. Hiring and promotion decisions still hinge heavily on track records: publication lists, grant income, citation counts and teaching evaluations. Committees often privilege clear markers of "independence" such as first- or last-author papers and major-funder awards, which advantages those with established networks and resources. Grant evaluation likewise combines assessments of novelty and feasibility with the applicant's prior productivity and institutional support; this favours safer projects and established investigators who can show preliminary data.

Publication metrics, e.g., journal prestige, impact factors, citation counts and derivative indices like h-index, are misused as convenient proxies for quality, despite well-known limitations and gaming risks (salami-slicing, citation cartels) (Ioannidis and Maniadis 2024). Institutional recognition typically amplifies these signals, concentrating prestige and funding within successful groups and elite institutions. Community norms in peer review practices, mentoring cultures, collaboration patterns and informal gatekeeping further shape outcomes and can reproduce inequities related to gender, race, discipline and geography.

These incentives and norms produce both productivity and distortions: they reward measurable outputs but often undervalue replication, negative results, teaching, and team science. Ongoing reforms seek to broaden what academia recognises, but systemic change remains uneven.

4 New proposals for reassessing the system of rewarding scholars

Traditional research assessment often reduces scholarly merit to quantitative indicators, neglecting contextual factors and the broader value of research to knowledge and society. In contrast, responsible research assessment (RRA) emphasises moving beyond narrow publication metrics, fostering diversity in research outputs, and implementing more holistic, transparent frameworks. Some of the most significant and recent initiatives include global movements such as DORA (San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment) (DORA Steering Committee 2012), the Leiden Manifesto (Hicks et al. 2015), and the CoARA Agreement (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) 2022). These initiatives advocate for systemic reform in academic evaluation. They call for research assessment based on qualitative judgment, the intrinsic value of research, and proper recognition of activities like data sharing, open science, peer review, and mentoring, not just journals or citation counts. The Metric Tide (Wilsdon et al. 2015) and the Hong Kong Principles (Moher et al. 2020) additionally shaped the current understanding of how responsible research assessment is viewed today.

Instruments are already in place to support the implementation of RRA, like the ‘Researcher Profile’, a service designed to help research funders and institutions implement their CoARA Agreement commitments (Xenou et al. 2025), the reference model for reporting in scientific institutions based on DORA (Mörsel 2026), or the collection of ‘Tools to Advance Research Assessment (TARA)’⁵.

As of May 2026, 12 member institutions of NFDI4Earth have signed DORA and 14 have signed CoARA.

5 Research data in research assessments

In Germany, the inclusion of researchers’ practices related to research data into responsible research assessment (RRA) schemes has been promoted, e.g., by the German Science and Humanities Council (Wissenschaftsrat 2020)⁶ and the Alliance Initiative “Digital Information in Science” (Alexander von Humboldt Foundation et al. 2025)⁷. The Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft DFG (German Research Foundation) also pointed out that assessing scholarship should draw on a broad spectrum of academic productivity rather than reflecting a narrow focus on bibliometric indicators. Related to that, data publication is explicitly mentioned as a possible

⁵ <https://sfdora.org/project-tara/>

⁶ Guideline 4: Recognition of Data and Software Work

⁷ “Positive effects arise from the FAIR curating and publication of research data and software, which the assessment process should, as a rule, recognise as scientific achievement.”

element in the assessment of scientific output (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft | AG Publikationswesen 2022).

Narrative CVs offer a structured written account of an individual's contributions and accomplishments, capturing a wider set of relevant skills and experiences than a conventional academic CV typically shows. This CV format allows to include and feature data publications as an accepted publication format. The use of narrative CVs in research grant applications has recently increased (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft 2024; Research on Research Institute (RoRI) et al. 2025), but in academic job recruitment this instrument is still rarely used (e.g., Kip and Dirnagl 2024). DFG allows in narrative CVs in addition to a maximum of ten contributions in the more commonly used formats up to ten further publicly available research results from a variety of publication formats, such as preprints, data sets or software packages. However, data publications were, so far, only very rarely mentioned in narrative CVs for DFG grant applications (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft 2024). The Charité narrative CV template (Kip and Dirnagl 2024) promotes research data publications to be included in the list of the five most important publications, and the description of data sharing strategies of the applicant is encouraged.

However, when viewed in a broader context, recognising researchers' practices related to research data in research assessments has not yet become widely established. Activities related to research data play a minor role in institutional review, promotion, and tenure policies (Pontika et al. 2022) and, as a side note, are even not mentioned at all as a criterion in a recent study on regional and institutional trends in assessment for academic promotion (Lim et al. 2025).

Future reward systems cannot ignore the fact that even responsible research evaluations still encompass fundamental ranking and resource allocation functions and that researchers will not only fully welcome the envisioned new research assessment schemes, but also feel intrinsic resistance (Muhonen and Himanen 2024). To ensure that changes to research assessments benefit, rather than worsen, research practices and researchers' working conditions, the voices and opinions of researchers themselves should be part and parcel in all activities on restructuring research assessment (see, e.g., Aubert Bonn and Pinxten 2021).

Quality of research data

One reason for the lack of recognition of activities related to research data is that the quality of the central product, a (published) data set, is difficult to assess. That is very much different compared to book and journal publications, which are still the major research products that are used for research assessments in academia. There are well accepted quality controls for these items in place: the contemporary scholarly publishing system depends on reviewers to conduct peer review; in this role they evaluate research and furnish editors with assessments that

inform publication decisions. For other research products like research data, determination of quality is still far from being as developed and established. The concepts of 'FAIR' (Wilkinson et al. 2016) and 'open' (Wildman and Lewis 2022) data are today often promoted to provide a framework for quality (NFDI4Earth Consortium 2024). Inspired by the FAIR principles, global quality assessment guidelines for digital data have been developed (with practical recommendations for the Earth science community) by Peng et al. (2022). The authors state that the guidelines bring "the Earth science community one step closer to standardising the curation and representation of dataset quality information."

Research data repositories significantly contribute to data quality, as most of them provide a formal assessment of the published datasets, and many of them perform additional data review of some form for at least some of the published datasets (Kindling and Strecker 2022). However, the survey of Kindling and Strecker (2022) showed that approaches to and the maturity of quality assurance measures for data repositories are diverse and that the results of the quality assessments are rarely shared publicly by the repositories. Stvilia et al. (2025) conducted a systematic analysis of data quality assurance practices in research data repositories, resulting in conceptualising a data quality assurance model for research data repositories. Such model may inform the design and development of future data quality assurance workflows and tools. Research data repository managers may also take advantage of the recently published data quality assurance ontology for designing, evaluating and integrating data quality assurance workflows (Lee et al. 2025).

Research data metrics

Usage metrics, e.g., citation counts of research data sets, have been promoted to be used to capture more diverse contributions to science to measure scientific impact and success. Using the Scholarly Link eXchange (Scholix) framework that aims to improve the links between scientific literature and research data, Cousijn et al. (2019) described a workflow for aggregating article-data links to count data citations. Hood and Sutherland (2021) describe a novel author-level metric, the data-index, which values both dataset output (number of datasets) and impact (number of data-index citations), designed to complement other metrics of scientific success.

A comparison of dataset citation coverage across several major bibliographic sources showed that the accuracy and comprehensiveness of dataset citations is very variable today (Gerasimov et al. 2024), implying that there are challenges ahead before such data-level metrics are available in a sufficient quality.

Castell et al. (2024) envisioned a quality indicator for research data and research software publications that integrates multiple dimensions of quality into one resulting number (the "quality indicator") which could be used in research assessments. This promising approach

was developed by the Helmholtz Association and addressed the following questions (Castell et al. 2024):

1. What quality criteria should be considered?
2. How to measure each of the quality criteria?
3. How to condense individual quality measures into one number, the quality indicator? In addition, for practicability,
4. How to collect the quality measures for the most part in an automated fashion?

The described approach to derive multi-dimensional quality indicators for data products is currently still in the development phase⁸. For software publications, however, quality indicators have been already published (Juckeland et al. 2025).

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⁸ See, e.g., developments at the Helmholtz Association: Valuing what matters: Developing new approaches to research assessment <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2942788>

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